

SEROPREVALENCE OF MAREK'S DISEASE VIRUS ANTIBODY IN CHICKENS FROM
THREE ZONES OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Blood samples from jugular veins were randomly obtained from 2,452 commercially improved and indigenous chickens from 36 flocks in Abuja, Kaduna, Bauchi, Plateau and Nasarawa States of Nigeria. Based on suspected Marek's disease (MD) outbreaks that needed follow up, the study area was chosen. Commercial flocks were mostly kept on deep litter with few in battery cage system with clinically suspected MD. Agar gel precipitin test (AGPT) was used to test sera sampled for Marek's disease virus (MDV) antibodies. Herpes turkey virus vaccine was mostly given by the farmers to control MD; some farmers believed chicks from hatcheries might have been vaccinated while other farmers had no idea of any MD vaccination status. The indigenous chickens had no records of vaccination and were all on free range. Marek's disease virus (HPRS-16) positive standard antigen and serum were commercially obtained from Veterinary Laboratory Agency (VLA-UK). Analysis of risk factors associated with seropositivity of MDV antibodies in commercial and indigenous chickens; univariate and multivariate logistic regression was done. A factor or independent variable of interest was considered to have an influence on seropositivity with statistically significant ($p \leq 0.05$). The overall seroprevalence of MD was 66.0% ($P < 0.0001$) which has increased since it was first diagnosed in Nigeria. The detection of MDV antibodies in unvaccinated improved and unvaccinated indigenous chickens indicated that they were exposed to MD field virus. This study gave current findings on Marek's disease in this area. A nationwide screening of chickens against Marek's disease is needed for epidemiological study and biosecurity control measures.

KEYWORDS: Seroprevalence, Marek's disease virus, antibodies, chickens, Nigeria.

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INTRODUCTION

Marek's disease (MD) is a lymphomatous and neuropathic disease mainly of domestic fowl caused by a Galid herpesvirus 2 (serotype 1), an *alphaherpesvirus* (Witter and Schat, 2003). Out of the three serotypes of Marek's disease virus (serotype 1, 2 and 3), serotype 1 is believed to be the pathogenic which is of economic importance worldwide (Witter *et al.*, 2005). Field diagnosis of MD is based on clinical signs, gross or microscopic lesions (Nair *et al.*, 2008 and OIE, 2010). Infection by MD virus is detected by virus isolation and the demonstration of viral antigen or antibodies (Adene, 1980; OIE, 2010). In chickens, Marek's disease occurs at 3–4 weeks of age or older and is most common between 12 and 30 weeks of age (Schat and Nair, 2008; OIE, 2010).

Under field conditions, most chickens become infected with MDV during the first few weeks of life and then carry the infection throughout their lives, often without developing overt disease (OIE, 2010). The evolutions of MD virus variants are likely to be the cause of MD outbreaks in vaccinated flocks (Witter *et al.*, 2005). The applications of different diagnostic procedures are widely applied for MD (Adene, 1983; OIE, 2004 and Zelnik, 2004). Antibodies to MDV develop within 1–2 weeks of infection are detected by the agar gel precipitin test

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(OIE, 2010). This study was carried out to determine the seroprevalence of MD in some towns with outbreaks in Nigeria using agar gel precipitin test (AGPT).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

The study areas were chosen based mostly on the ongoing reported suspected MD cases that needed follow up and conveniences which included Plateau and Nasarawa states and FCT (Abuja) in North-central zone; Kaduna state (North-west zone) and Bauchi state (North-east zone), Ekong *et al.*, 2012). In Kaduna state, samples collected were from aviation, sabon gari, samaru and gadan mallam Abuja road. Samples from plateau state involved jos north, jos south, jos east, pankshin and mangu. Nasarawa state samples were from lafia, akwanga, nyanya and masaka. Samples from FCT were from wuse and karu. The samples from bauchi state came from toro area. The type of birds involved were mostly MD unvaccinated indigenous chickens and commercially improved vaccinated and unvaccinated chickens from poultry farms, live bird markets and household birds. Blood was obtained from jugular veins from commercial and household birds while market live birds blood from slaughtered birds. The commercial flocks were mostly kept on deep litter with few in battery cage system that were apparently healthy and clinically with suspected MD, which the farm size can reach above 5000 chickens. The source of feed was commercial or self-milling while the indigenous chickens were extensively managed in the study areas. Indigenous chickens of different ages and sources were housed together mostly in the household chickens while the commercially improved chicks were mostly sourced from the southern part of the country.

Figure 1: Map of Nigeria showing location of States where sera were sampled for Marek's disease in chickens (Map of study site was designed in ArcView GIS version 3.1).

Sample size

The sample size for the seroepidemiological survey for MD was determined by using the method of Mahajan (1997) which used the formula:

$$N = Z^2 pq / L^2$$

where N = sample size (minimum), Z = 1.96; q = 1-p ; L = allowable error = 5%; P = prevalence rate 39.5% (based on Adene and Hill, 1977); N = 376 (minimum sample size). This number was multiplied by 4 to obtain 1,469. At the end of the survey, 2,452 sera were collected and tested for antibodies against MDV.

Sampling technique

Blood samples were randomly taken from 20 birds in a flock without replacement. A data collection form was filled to identify location, age, source, species, and type of bird, vaccination status, flock size and source of feed.

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Blood collection

Using 5 ml syringes, about 1.5 to 3 ml of blood from the jugular veins were collected from both commercial and indigenous chickens. The syringes were slanted and the blood was allowed to clot at room temperature and sera were transferred into labeled cryovials and stored in a freezer until used.

Preparation of agar gel

One percent of agar rose, 8% sodium chloride making up to 100 ml of phosphate buffer saline (PBS) with pH 7.4, and the mixture was boiled and placed in a water bath at 56°C. (ii) 15 ml of agar dispensed into medium size Petri dishes (50 by 150 mm) to form a thickness of about 3mm. (iii) Wells were punched in the agar using a standard template with a centre well and 6 wells spaced at equal distance around the centre well. The diameter of wells was approximately 5.3 mm and the wells were about 2.4 mm apart (Plate 1) as described by OIE (2010).

Qualitative agar gel precipitin test

Marek's disease virus (HPRS-16) positive standard antigen and serum lot No PA156, Batch No MP 062 Batch 11-4-84 and PA0157, Batch No MP 063 BR were purchased from veterinary laboratory agencies united kingdom (VLA-UK) for AGPT as recommended. Using micropipette, the standard antigen was placed in the centre well and the standard antiserum in alternate exterior wells to serve as controls. Test sera were placed in the remaining wells. The Petri dishes were covered with lids and incubated in a humid jar at 37°C for 24 hours. Daily observations for precipitin lines between the standard antigen, serum and the tested sera for three days were carried out. The results were read over a lamp in a dark room. They were scored for positive meaning visible precipitin line (plate. 1) or negative means no precipitin line developed.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was conducted using the MedCalc statistical software version 11.2.90. (2010). The outcome (dependent) variable was individual Marek's disease virus (MDV) seropositivity status using AGPT, coded as zero (negative serum) or one (positive serum). In the analysis of risk factors associated with the seropositivity of MDV in the commercial as well as indigenous chickens, univariate and multivariate logistic regression was by using StataCorp (2009). A factor or independent variable of interest had an influence on seropositivity (significant) at a probability level of $\leq 5\%$.

RESULTS

Line of precipitin was formed between positive MD serum and antigen. Line of precipitin was formed between positive test sera and MD standard antigen and no line between negative test sera (plate.1). The results were transferred into laboratory result sheet. Then transferred into field sample form.

Plate 1: Results' cross section of A and B showing agar gel precipitin test of Marek's disease positive lines of precipitation. A and B = Precipitin lines in positive field cases. Arrows at 12 O'clock in plate A and B were pointing at the standard serum. T= test sera in the surrounding wells from field samples while negative control at 6 O'clock in plate A. The centre wells contain the standard MD antigen.

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Location

Two thousand four hundred and fifty two (1840 from North-central-Plateau, Nasarawa and FCT; 592 from North-west- Kaduna and 20 from North-east- Bauchi) sera were randomly collected and examined for MDV antibody by AGPT. The overall seroprevalence of MD in the study areas was 66.0% (Table 1). The results obtained showed that the seroprevalence of MD in the North-central, North-west, and North-east was 63.8%, 72.1% and 80.0% respectively. Overall, there was a significant higher risk in the North-west zone (RR 1.13), North-east zone (RR 1.25) compared with the North-central zone. Result from the univariable analysis (Table 3) indicated that a significant higher risk of MD infection; 1.52, 1.28, 1.16 and 1.18 among chickens from FCT (Abuja), Bauchi, Kaduna, Nasarawa respectively, compared with chickens from Plateau State.

Age group of Chickens

There was no significant difference in seroprevalence of MD among age groups (Table 3) when compared age 5-10weeks with 11-18 and >18 weeks (P values = 0.0836 and 0.6578, RR= 0.97 and 1.1.2 respectively). Chicks sourced from the southern part of Nigeria showed a significantly higher risk (RR 1.14) of developing antibodies to MDV compared to those from the northern Nigeria (Table 3).

Type of Chickens

There was no significant difference in seroprevalence (Table 1) of MD between commercial (66.9%) and indigenous (63.7%) (RR 1.05, 95% CI: 0.99-1.12, p = 0.1249).

Vaccination as risk factor among chickens

The relative risk of MD among unvaccinated commercial chickens compared with unvaccinated indigenous chickens 1.19 (95% CI: 1.05 – 1.34) was highly significant (p = 0.0062). The relative risk of MD among vaccinated commercial chickens compared to unvaccinated commercial chickens was 1.2 (95% CI: 1.05 – 1.28) was significant (p = 0.0039) (Table 2). The relative risk of MD among vaccinated chickens compared to unvaccinated chickens was 1.01 (95% CI: 0.95 – 1.07), was not significant (p = 0.843) (Table 2). Farms with more than 5,000 birds had a significant higher risk (RR 1.37). Farms that used self-milled feed had a significant higher risk (RR 1.23) of MD infection compared to farms that used commercial feeds.

Table1: Seroprevalence of Marek’s disease in poultry from five states of Nigeria, 2005 - 2009

Variable	Seroprevalence of MD %		
	(that tested positive MD/ Total)	95% CI	p- value
Study Area			
Overall seroprevalence of MD	65.9 (1617/2452)	63.9 – 67.8	< 0.0001
Studied Zones			
North-west (Kaduna)	72.1 (427/592)	68.3 – 75.7	< 0.0001
North-east (Bauchi)	80.0 (16/20)	56.3 – 94.3	0.0021
North central(Plateau, Nasarawa and FCT)	63.8(1174/1840)	61.6-66.0	< 0.0001
Type of Chickens			
Commercial	66.9 (1138/1700)	64.6 – 69.1	< 0.0001
Indigenous	63.7 (479/752)	60.2 – 67.1	< 0.0001

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Table 2: Univariable analysis of vaccination versus no vaccination among commercial and indigenous chickens from 2005-2009.

Variable	Tested Positive MD/ Total (%)	Relative risk	95% CI	p – value
No vaccination				
Unvacc.Commercial chickens	107/140 (76.4)	1.2	1.05-1.34	0.0062
Unvacc. Indigenous chickens	204/317 (64.4)	1	RF	
Commercial farm				
Unvacc.Commercial chickens	107/140 (76.4)	1.2	1.05-1.28	0.0039
Vacc. Commercial chickens	1031/1560 (66.1)	1	RF	

NB: Unvacc = Unvaccinated chickens, Vacc. = Vaccinated chickens, RF = Reference group

Table 3: Univariable analysis of demographic risk factors for Marek’s disease infection in Chickens, 2005 – 2009

Variable	Positive MD/total (%)	Relative Risk	95% CI	p – value
Location				
Abuja	19/20 (95.0)	1.52	1.37-1.69	<0.0001
Bauchi	16/20 (80.0)	1.28	1.03-1.60	0.028
Kaduna	427/592 (72.1)	1.16	1.09-1.23	<0.0001
Nasarawa	132/180 (73.3)	1.18	1.07-1.29	0.0009
Plateau	1023/1640 (62.4)	1	RF	
Zone				
North-west(Kaduna)	427/592 (72.1)	1.13	1.06-1.20	0.0001
North-east(Bauchi)	16/20 (80.0)	1.25	1.01-1.57	0.046
Central(Plateau, Nasarawa, FCT)	1174/1840 (63.8)	1	RF	
Type of Chickens				
Commercial	1138/1700 (66.9)	1.05	0.99-1.12	0.1249
Local	479/752 (63.7)	1	RF	
Flock size				
5000	157/180 (87.2)	1.37	1.28-1.46	<0.0001
>1000-5000	322/485 (66.4)	1.04	0.97-1.12	0.259
1-1000	1138/1787 (63.7)	1	RF	
Age				
>18 weeks	367/540 (67.9)	0.97	0.85-1.11	0.6578
11-18 weeks	263/335 (78.5)	1.12	0.99-1.28	0.0836
1-10 weeks	84/120 (70.0)	1	RF	
Type of feed				
Self milling	361/480 (75.2)	1.23	1.15-1.32	<0.0001
Commercial	626/1025 (61.1)	1	RF	
Source of Chicks				
South	302/400 (75.5)	1.14	1.04-1.24	0.0033
North	295/445 (66.3)	1	RF	

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DISCUSSION

Plateau had the highest seroprevalence for Marek's disease virus (MDV) antibodies could be due to high concentration of poultry farms and chickens. It was possible that the level of Marek's disease (MD) vaccination was also high in plateau state. Chickens between the ages of 11 and 18 weeks had the highest seroprevalence for MDV was because they were mostly pullets reaching the point of lay. This agreed with similar reports that in chickens, MD occurs at 3- 4 weeks of age or older and is most common between 12 and 30 weeks of age (Nair *et al.*, 2008; Schat and Nair, 2008 and OIE, 2010). Chicks sourced from the southern part of the country had the highest seroprevalence for MDV was due to high concentration of both hatcheries and commercial poultry farms. It was possible that the chance of MDV exposure was high which agreed with the findings of Dunn *et al.* (2010) that the virus is ubiquitous especially within commercial poultry flocks.

The prevalence reported by Nawathe *et al.* (1978) was higher in indigenous chickens than in improved commercial poultry was in agreement with the seroprevalence obtained in this study, which could be due to exposure to the field virus. Commercially improved chickens (Table, 2) that were high with seroprevalence for MDV could be due to MDV vaccination, genetic susceptibility and chickens that were in close contact could be exposed to MD infection. Unvaccinated commercial chickens were higher than unvaccinated indigenous chickens with seroprevalence for MDV antibody could be due to genetic susceptibility; infected chicks' sources and management problems like stress factors could easily exposed the flock to infection. Vaccinated commercial birds had high seroprevalence for MDV than unvaccinated commercial birds could be due to MD vaccination status. The overall vaccinated chickens were higher than unvaccinated birds with seroprevalence for MDV antibody could be due to vaccines exposure. On poultry population in Nigeria (Adene and Oguntade, 2006), chickens of flock size above 5000 had the highest seroprevalence for MDV could be due to close contact, since MD spread horizontally when exposed to MDV infection. Self-milling feeds were higher than the commercial feeds with seroprevalence for MDV, could be due to high chances of feed contamination thereby exposing the flocks to MD infection.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The overall MD seroprevalence (66.0%) was high. The seroprevalence of MD was higher in the North and the risk of the disease was highest in the North West. Type of birds indicated that seroprevalence was high in both commercially improved and indigenous chickens.

There should be strict adherence to biosecurity practices among poultry farmers to reduce early exposure of chicks to field MDV before establishment of vaccine immunity. There should be proper handling of MD vaccines during thawing and reconstitution by experience staff to ensure adequate doses and administration. Future research is needed to screen more avian species for MDV antibodies, isolation of the MD virus and subsequent characterization of the field virus for pathogenecity. Commercial and local chickens be screened for MDV genetic resistance.

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